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V ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN PROCESS INDUSTRY EEM2023

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023

REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA
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**UNIVERSITY OF EAST SARAJEVO
FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY ZVORNIK**

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VIII INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS

***ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN
PROCESS INDUSTRY***

EEM2023

**UNDER THE AUSPICES OF
MINISTRY OF ECONOMY AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP OF THE REPUBLIC OF
SRPSKA**

AND

ACADEMY OF SCIENCES AND ARTS OF THE REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA

**JAHORINA, MARCH 20-23, 2023
REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA**

PUBLISHER

UNIVERSITY OF EAST SARAJEVO

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ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN PROCESS INDUSTRY

PUBLISHED: 2023

ISBN: 978-99955-81-44-2

The authors have full responsibility for the originality and content of their own papers.

UNDER THE AUSPICES OF

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ENVIRONMENT

ENV-01	<u>PHENOL REMOVAL FROM SYNTHETIC WASTEWATER BY ELECTRO-FENTON PROCESS</u> Tijana Đuričić, Borislav N. Malinović, Helena Prosen	181
ENV-02	<u>THE PRESENCE OF MICROPLASTICS IN THE ENVIRONMENT, SOURCES OF HUMAN EXPOSURE, AND POTENTIAL HEALTH EFFECTS</u> Jelena Vuković, Slavko Smiljanić, Milomirka Obrenović, Una Marčeta, Bogdana Vujić	182
ENV-03	<u>INFLUENCE OF NOISE ON THE QUALITY OF THE ENVIRONMENT IN NOVI SAD</u> Branko Savic, Anita Petrovic, Bozo Ilić, Nenad Janjic	183
ENV-04	<u>APPLICATION OF GRAPE BIOSTIMULATORS AND THEIR STABILITY UNDER SOLAR LIGHT IN RAINWATER</u> Sanja Armaković, Maria Savanović, Andrijana Bilić, Mladen Kalajdžić, Jelena Kalajdžić, Dragoslav Ivanišević, Igor Savić, Teodora Gajo, Stevan Armaković	184
ENV-05	<u>PLASMA TREATMENT OF POLLUTED WATER</u> Monica Magureanu, Florin Bilea, Corina Bradu	185
ENV-06	<u>UV-FILTERS BENZOPHENONES AS LIGANDS FOR ANDROGEN RECEPTORS-IN SILICO EVALUATION</u> Maja Milanović, Nataša Milošević, Jovana Drljača, Nataša Milić	186
ENV-07	<u>LEAD AS BIOMARKER OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION AMONG MALE PATIENTS WITH LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA IN VOJVODINA</u> Nataša Milošević, Danica Szadanić Velikić, Maja Milanović, Sanja Bijelović, Mirka Lukić Šarkanović, Jovana Drljača, Nataša Milić	187
ENV-08	<u>SOURCES OF OUTDOOR POLLUTION AMONG MALE PATIENTS WITH LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA IN VOJVODINA</u> Nataša Milošević, Danica Szadanić Velikić, Maja Milanović, Mirjana Ševo, Jovana Drljača, Nataša Milić	188
ENV-09	<u>ARE MICRO-/NANOPLASTICS THE NOVEL GLOBAL HEALTH CHALLENGE?</u> Maja Milanović, Nataša Milošević, Milorad Španović, Jan Sudji, Jovana Drljača, Nataša Milić	189
ENV-10	<u>RISK ASSESSMENT OF LEACHATE POLLUTION OF THE WATER RESOURCES IN THE SAVA RIVER BASIN</u> Nebojša Knežević, Svjetlana Sredić	190
ENV-11	<u>PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WASTEWATER USING HORSE RADISH PEROXIDASE IMMOBILIZED ONTO MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES VIA GLUTARALDEHYDE</u> Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić	191
ENV-12	<u>IMPROVEMENT OF POTABLE WATER PREPARATION TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AT THE ILIDŽA SPRING PLANT</u> Nebojša Knežević, Igor Milunović	192
ENV-13	<u>CORRELATION BETWEEN ABUNDANCE OF MICROPLASTICS AND CONCENTRATION OF PHTHALATE ESTERS</u> Nataša Stojić, Ljiljana Čurčić, Dunja Prokić, Mira Pucarević	193
ENV-14	<u>ADSORPTION AND DEGRADATION POTENTIAL OF IMIDACLOPRID INSECTICIDE THROUGH CHEMICALLY MODIFIED CELLULOSE MATERIAL</u> Nataša Knežević, Jovana Bošnjaković, Marija Vuksanović, Katarina Jovanović-Radovanov, Srećko Manasijević, Adela Egelja, Aleksandar Marinković	194

ENV-15	<u>OXIDIZED COTTON FABRIC CHEMICAL FUNCTIONALIZED FOR CATIONIC DYES ADSORPTION</u> Jovana Bošnjaković, Ivan Đuričković, Jovana Milanović, Dragana Grujić, Aleksandar Marinković, Srećko Manasijević, Milena Milošević	195
ENV-16	<u>EFFECT OF THE SYNTHETIC ZEOLITE DOSE ON REMOVAL EFFICIENCY OF HEAVY METAL FROM WASTEWATER</u> Slavko Smiljanić, Jelena Vuković, Aleksandar Došić, Zoran Obrenović	196
ENV-17	<u>INVESTIGATION ON THE POSSIBILITY OF USING ACTIVATED CARBON FOR COLOR CORRECTION IN THE TREATMENT OF LEACHATE LOADED WITH HEAVY METALS</u> Slavko Smiljanić, Jelena Vuković, Zoran Obrenović, Aleksandar Došić	197
ENV-18	<u>ENHANCED BIOLOGICAL PHOSPHORUS REMOVAL – BASIC PRINCIPLES AND TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS</u> Slavko Smiljanić, Sofren Pavlović, Alija Salkunić, Jelena Vuković	198
ENV-19	<u>INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF CONTACT TIME ON THE SORPTION EFFICIENCY OF HEAVY METALS FROM WASTEWATER BY SYNTHETIC ZEOLITE</u> Slavko Smiljanić, Jelena Vuković, Aleksandar Došić, Zoran Obrenović	199
ENV-20	<u>DETERMINATION OF HEAVY METAL CONTENTS IN STINGING NETTLE FROM DIFFERENT LOCALITIES IN SERBIA</u> Kosana Popović, Mirjana Antonijević Nikolić, Jelena Đuričić Milanković, Dragan Ranković, Bojana Milutinović, Branka Dražić, Slađana Tanasković	200
ENV-21	<u>IMPROVING SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT AS IMPORTANT STEP TO SUSTAINABILITY: SEPARATION OF WASTE IN HOUSEHOLDS</u> Mirjana Antonijević Nikolić, Jelena Đuričić Milanković, Kosana Popović, Slađana Tanasković	201
ENV-22	<u>POLLUTANT CLASSIFICATION IN THE NORTHEASTERN PART OF PODMAJEVICA</u> Jagoda Krsmanović, Ljubica Vasiljević, Snežana Radulović, Dušanka Cvijanović, Rado Savić	202
ENV-23	<u>MECHANISM AND PARAMETERS OF THE EBPR PROCESS</u> Sofren Pavlović, Slavko Smiljanić, Slađana Petronić	203
ENV-24	<u>CEMENT PRODUCTION INDUSTRY: IMPACT ON AMBIENT AIR QUALITY</u> Jelena Đuričić Milanković, Dragana Đorđević, Kosana Popović	204
ENV-25	<u>ECO-SUSTAINABLE GREEN REMEDIATION: POTENTIAL OF DANDELION (<i>TARAXACUM SP.</i>) IN REMEDIATION OF SOIL CONTAMINATED WITH HEAVY METALS</u> Jelena Đuričić-Milanković, Kosana Popović, Bojan Damjanović, Mirjana Antonijević-Nikolić	205
ENV-26	<u>CENTIPEDES (CHILOPODA) AS BIOINDICATORS OF SOIL POLLUTION</u> Bojan Mitić, Ljubica Vasiljević, Slavica Borković-Mitić	206
ENV-27	<u>PLANT MEDIATED SYNTHETIZED NZVI SUPPORTED ON BIOCHAR IN THE TREATMENT OF DIFFERENT ENVIRONMENTAL MEDIA</u> Dragana Tomašević Pilipović, Nataša Slijepčević, Anita Leovac Maćerak, Đurđa Kerkez, Milena Bečelić-Tomin, Dejan Krčmar, Jelena Beljin	207

**PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WASTEWATER USING HORSERADISH PEROXIDASE
IMMOBILIZED ONTO MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES VIA
GLUTARALDEHYDE**

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Abstract

Phenolic components present in industrial wastewaters could negatively affect the aquatic ecosystem and human health if they are not properly treated before discharge into waterways. The treatment that can effectively remove phenol from water is a biological process using peroxidases. In the presence of hydrogen peroxide, peroxidases lead to the polymerization of phenol, whereby the resulting polymers are precipitated and thus separated from the water. A significant advantage is achieved when peroxidases are used in an immobilized form on a suitable solid support. In addition to enabling its reuse in several consecutive cycles; the immobilized enzyme is significantly more stable compared to the free enzyme. In this paper, the effectiveness of the application of immobilized horseradish peroxidase onto surface modified carbon nanotubes in the removal of phenol from wastewater was examined. Carbon nanotubes were functionalized with concentrated nitric acid and used as solid support for peroxidase immobilization via glutaraldehyde. A phenol solution in ultra-pure deionized water was used as a model of phenol-containing wastewater. Using immobilized horseradish peroxidase (0.6 U/ml), 82% of phenol was removed after 2 hours of reaction. It can be concluded that bio-catalytic treatment of phenolic wastewater can significantly reduce the content of phenolic pollutants.

Key words: Immobilized peroxidase, Multi-walled carbon nanotubes, Phenol removal, Wastewater treatment

Acknowledgement: The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia under Grant (OI 172059, 451-03-68/2022-14/200134) and COST action (CA20133) FULLRECO4US.